

D7.10 Organization of a Press-conference and industry workshops at dedicated film festivals

Project: Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness - REBOOT

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2. PROJECT SUMMARY

The REBOOT project aims to connect the existing strengths, identify and overcome weaknesses and plan for future competitiveness in the fields of policy, practice and experience. More concretely, the project's objectives are, on the one hand, to explore the long-standing strengths and pervasive gaps in European competitiveness and policies for competitiveness. This includes ways of 'measuring' 'analysing' and 'evaluating' the impact of policies and strategic pathways. On the other hand, the project aspires to place attention to the active preparation for the future in the area of audiences by exploring audience preferences and their generation, as well as modes of film content production. The latter are elements which today's youth will carry and engage with in the coming decades as makers and consumers, as well as industry and policy leaders. Therefore, the consortium interrogates not only the 'what is' but also the 'what has been' and 'what will be' with fresh lenses. REBOOT's ambition is to provide a full set of knowledge of the European film industry, which maximises its existing strengths, combined with strategic and tactical dimensions of action for the optimisation of the potential held in European youth publics, understood both as emerging audiences and as citizens. Specifically, the ambition of the project combines several dimensions, which reinforce each other but are listed separately for analytical purposes (and in no particular order): a) increasing support for young people's engagement with European film; b) strengthening the place of the EU in the global audiovisual economy, particularly in light of the rise of video on demand (VOD); c) supporting cultural diversity in the EU film industry; d) addressing the need for a different understanding of competitiveness and relevant indicators in this context; and e) recognising and supporting the importance for the EU of film and, more broadly, of the cultural and creative sector as a geopolitical asset.

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3. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 7.10 (M24) Press Conference and Industry Workshops at Dedicated Film Festivals is a key component of Work Package 7 (Dissemination), outlining the visibility and engagement activities undertaken by the REBOOT project and its consortium partners. A deliverable led by Université Côte d'Azur (UCA), this report provides a detailed account of the project's participation in major industry events, workshops, and film festivals. These activities have served as crucial platforms for disseminating preliminary findings, fostering dialogue, and building strategic connections between the REBOOT project and key industry stakeholders.

A major highlight of these efforts was the ***Marché du Film at the Cannes Film Festival***, which took place from on May 15, 2024. This prestigious event, recognised as one of the most influential markets for the global film industry, provided an opportunity for the REBOOT project team to engage with professionals from various sectors. A dedicated panel discussion featured representatives from REBOOT who engaged with an interested audience, presenting insights on the project's research and objectives. The discussion attracted a diverse group of participants, including filmmakers, producers, policymakers, and industry representatives, facilitating an exchange of ideas on the evolving landscape of film and media.

Another significant event was the ***Cultural Audiovisual Heritage for the Public Good and European Competitiveness workshop***, held in Warsaw from January 22 to 25, 2025. The workshop took place within a three-day event in Warsaw under the umbrella of the *Knowledge Exchange, setting the stage for public service media to thrive in the Age of Platforms* event.

This gathering brought together representatives from academia, public institutions, and the film industry to explore the role of cultural audiovisual heritage in fostering public engagement and economic competitiveness within the European audiovisual sector. Through presentations, discussions, and collaborative exchanges, participants addressed the importance of policy frameworks, funding mechanisms, and institutional support in preserving and promoting audiovisual heritage.

Additionally, the ***SAWA*** (Screen Advertising World Association) Convention, held in Nice from February 11 to 14, 2024, convened leading figures from cinema advertising, marketing, and audience engagement. This event served for the Reboot representatives as a platform for discussions on advertising strategies, technological advancements, and the evolving role of cinema in the digital landscape. With cinema advertising emerging as a powerful medium in an increasingly

fragmented media environment, the convention underscored the significance of audience attention metrics and digital innovations. REBOOT's participation in the event allowed for the integration of academic perspectives on creativity in cinema and advertising, contributing to ongoing industry conversations on media transformation.

Furthermore, the **UNESCO Week of Sound**, hosted at the Georges Méliès Campus in Cannes from January 20 to 29, 2023, provided an interdisciplinary forum focused on sound-related creativity, technological advancements, and professional trajectories. By bringing together experts from artistic, technical, and academic backgrounds, the event offered a panoramic examination of contemporary developments in sound studies. Discussions ranged from the artistic dimensions of sound production to the impact of new technologies on film and media, offering a comprehensive perspective on the role of sound in contemporary audiovisual industries.

Through active participation in these key events, the REBOOT project has successfully strengthened its presence within the audiovisual sector, contributed to critical discussions on film and media policy, and established valuable collaborations with industry stakeholders.

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4. EVENTS, WORKSHOP AND PRESS CONFERENCE

4.1 Conference at Cannes Festival

On 15 May 2024, the REBOOT research consortium participated in a panel discussion at the Marché du Film, a key industry event held during the Cannes Film Festival. The session brought together leading researchers to explore the evolving landscape of European audiovisual policies and the challenges facing the European film industry in an increasingly globalised market. Moderated by Jean-François Trubert (Université Côte d'Azur), the discussion featured Antonios Vlassis (University of Liège), Katharine Sarikakis (University of Vienna), and Evangelia Psychogiopoulou (University of Peloponnese).

Key topics included the historical evolution of European policies fostering competitiveness while preserving cultural diversity, tensions between economic imperatives and cultural sustainability, and the impact of digitalisation, platformisation, and globalisation on the European film ecosystem. The discussion underscored the importance of European co-productions, international distribution strategies, and linguistic factors in determining the global success of European films.

The REBOOT research employs a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative lexicometric analysis of 183 policy documents with qualitative textual analysis of legislative and regulatory frameworks. Empirical data collection has been a central component of the study, incorporating a large-scale survey and over 120 interviews with film professionals from both EU and non-EU countries, including Argentina, Brazil, Mexico, South Korea, South Africa, and Turkey. Additionally, a quantitative mapping of European films' presence in international markets was conducted using databases such as Lumiere, IMDb, and Box Office Mojo. This comprehensive methodology has allowed the project to assess the impact of policy measures on the global positioning of European cinema.

One of the key findings discussed during the panel was the evolving relationship between competitiveness and cultural diversity in EU audiovisual policies. While European institutions have historically sought to balance economic and cultural objectives, the increasing emphasis on market expansion and technological adaptation has sometimes led to tensions with cultural preservation efforts. The discussion also highlighted the significant role of language in the international circulation of European films, with English-language productions generally achieving greater market penetration. Furthermore, co-productions emerged as a crucial factor in enhancing competitiveness, fostering financial stability, and facilitating knowledge exchange. However, the absence of a unified EU strategy for international expansion remains a limitation, as each film is developed as an individual project rather than as part of a broader industry-wide approach.

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The impact of digitalisation and the rise of streaming platforms was another central theme of the discussion. While digital distribution offers new opportunities for European films, it also introduces challenges related to discoverability and market dominance by non-European platforms. The panel also addressed the importance of music production in film competitiveness, an aspect often overlooked in policy discussions. Advances in music scoring technologies, including artificial intelligence, are reshaping the industry, necessitating further adaptation in European film production processes.

In conclusion, the panel underscored the complex interplay between policy, market forces, and cultural imperatives in shaping the future of the European film industry. While economic considerations are increasingly prioritised in EU audiovisual policies, cultural diversity remains a fundamental principle guiding regulatory and funding decisions. The findings of the REBOOT project suggest that strategic policy adjustments are necessary to strengthen the global positioning of European cinema while ensuring that its cultural foundations remain intact. As technological advancements and market transformations continue to redefine the industry, fostering a synergy between competitiveness and cultural sustainability will be crucial for the future of European film.

CONFERENCES SERVICES

MARCHÉ DU FILM
14-22 MAY 2024

MY ACCOUNT EN
Register Now Schedule

Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness (Panel)

UNIVERSITÉ CÔTE D'AZUR REEBOOT universität wien

May 15, 2024, 12:00 - 13:00 GMT+2
The Viewpoint (Lérins)

How to connect existing strengths and plan for future competitiveness? we present a set of knowledge of the European film industry, which maximizes its existing strengths, combined with strategic and tactical dimensions of for the optimization of the potential held in European youth publics, understood both as emerging audiences and as citizens.

Speakers

<p>Evangelia Psychogiopoulou Assistant Professor, Senior Research Fellow Department of Political Science and International Relations, University of the Peloponnese, Hellenic Foundation for European and Foreign Policy</p>	
<p>Katharine Sarikakis Professor of Communication, Consortium Coordinator University of Vienna, Austria</p>	
<p>António Vlassis Associate Research Professor University of Liège, Center for International Relations Studies, Department of Political Science</p>	

Moderators

<p>Jean-François Trubert Music Professor, Université Côte d'Azur / CEO, Regional Campus for Jobs & Qualifications Creative and Cultural Industries / President, MIN4CI Foundation for ICC</p>	
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Figure 1. Announcement of the Conference at the Cannes Festival 2024 edition.

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Figure 2. Display of the conference at Cannes International Film Festival

Figure 3. Pictures of the audience during the Conference at International Film Festival in Cannes, Palais des Festivals.

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4.2. Cultural Audiovisual Heritage for the Public Good and European Competitiveness Workshop in Warsaw

On January 22, 2025, a workshop titled “Cultural Audiovisual Heritage for the Public Good and European Competitiveness” was held at the Zachęta - National Gallery of Art to discuss the film and media industry. The workshop aimed to explore the functioning of various European film markets, with a particular focus on film policy-making and the role of public institutions in supporting the film industry.

Organised by the University of Warsaw, a partner of the REBOOT project consortium, the event was held in collaboration with researchers from the PSM-AP project, Zachęta – National Gallery of Art, Creative Europe Desk Poland, and FINA – National Film Archive – Audiovisual Institute. As part of the REBOOT EU Horizon Europe project, the workshop took place within a three-day event in Warsaw under the umbrella of the Knowledge Exchange, setting the stage for public service media to thrive in the Age of Platforms.

The goal of Poland's REBOOT national workshop was to support the audiovisual and film industries by bringing together scholars, filmmakers, producers, and key state institutions. Participants discussed the concepts of Public Good and European Competitiveness in the context of global media platforms. The REBOOT initiative focused on research, societal impact, and policy-making contributions aimed at exploring Poland's and Europe's audiovisual heritage. Additionally, it sought to enhance access to archives from the pre-internet era, addressing the integration of production and distribution.

Approximately 60 people attended the workshop, actively engaging in the debate for nearly two hours. The workshop, structured as a debate, was led by Michał Głowacki from the University of Warsaw, who heads the Polish research team for the REBOOT project. Several experts participated in the discussion, including Tadeusz Kowalski from the National Broadcasting Council, Jacek Mikucki from the University of Warsaw, Gentiana Ramadani from the University of Vienna, Fernando Ramos Arenas from Complutense University of Madrid, Elżbieta Wysocka-Koerber from the National Film Archive - Audiovisual Institute (FINA), and Anita Zawisza from the University of Warsaw.

The event started with a welcome address by Michał Głowacki, who provided a brief overview of the workshop and the objectives of the Reboot research project. The guests were then welcomed by the Dean of the Faculty of Journalism, Information and Book Studies, Dariusz Kuźmina, as well as Agnieszka Pindera, the Director of the Zachęta National Gallery of Art, and Małgorzata Kielczewska,

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the Director of Creative Europe Desk Poland. These institutions, along with the National Film Archive-Audiovisual Institute (FINA), were co-organizers of the event. Following a brief introduction of the panellists by Michal Glowacki, the expert debate segment of the meeting commenced.

The debate began with a critical question aimed at offering a modern understanding of competitiveness in the film market. Michal Glowacki asked: Let's try to speak about the lenses of today's competitiveness. What does the competitive mean to you in terms of film, audio, visual and in terms of history? Gentiana Ramadani emphasised that defining the concept of competitiveness in today's rapidly changing world, influenced by technology, is challenging. This is why the Reboot project was initiated, aiming to redefine this concept and understand the dynamics of the contemporary film industry. Focusing on the European film market, Ramadani pointed out that competitiveness relies on finding a balance between regulation and creativity. She also highlighted the importance of a shared understanding of competitiveness and public good among both filmmakers and audiences. Fernando Ramos Arenas noted that contemporary film competitiveness should be viewed from a historical perspective to identify both commonalities and differences. It's important to remember that the film industry is constantly evolving, affecting film production, distribution, and exposure. Consequently, the concept of competitiveness in the film market has also changed, taking into account the cultural and social differences among various film markets worldwide. He also referenced research findings to support his points: "We started the conversation with our stakeholders with this idea of asking them about competitiveness, and we ended then usually talking about sustainability." Thus, it is crucial to maintain a balanced presentation of content in the era of global streaming platforms such as Netflix. Jacek Mikucki pointed out the multiplicity and diversity of film markets, which also makes it difficult to have one holistic definition of competitiveness in the audiovisual sector: "Plenty of people from South America coming to Europe to study to, for example, film direction, camera operation and so on but in the end, they don't follow exactly the same path which Europe promotes." Thus, the concept of competitiveness should be considered through the lens of regions around the world.

Tadeusz Kowalski, an audiovisual policymaker for more than 40 years, stressed that due to his experience and knowledge, it is extremely difficult to define contemporary competitiveness in the film industry. As he stressed: "I think that we had to think about very wide concept of the competitiveness." He noted that at the end of the day, all film entities are competing to keep the attention of audiences, which in turn affects economic competition in the film market. This emphasis on the audience's role in shaping competitiveness not only underscores their importance but also makes them feel valued and influential in the industry. Anita Zawisza spoke about the important role of diversity in the film industry: "When it comes to the stakeholders, when it comes to the subject of

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the movie, of the TV series, it is very important to remember about diversity.” She pointed out that the largest markets in the world are the US and China. Especially the film market in China has a completely different approach to competitiveness, because they don't consider the European or American market, due to China's internal values and policies, which differ from those of, for example, Europe. Besides, the target group is the Chinese citizens themselves, and it is for them that film policy is created.

Later in the conversation, Fernando Ramos Arenas referred to the enormous role of new communications solutions: “you have like this useful suspects over production, huge impact of the VOD platforms, it conglomerates, automation.” He added that Hollywood productions heavily influence the European film market. So competitiveness is often considered only by these two film markets. In turn, Tadeusz Kowalski cited data showing the European market's significant role: “In 2023, it was produced 3300 films in Europe.” He also pointed out that an average of 30 feature-length films are produced annually in Poland. Ramos Arenas acknowledged the problem in film distribution by independent filmmakers: “if you talk to the, to the producers, they may independent producers, they may say that's a problem of distribution or people are not reaching the audiences because somebody's not making the job rightly.” Gentiana Ramadani, on the other hand, pointed out the key role of film policies, especially European ones: “European countries provide a lot of support, of course, to their film industries, but they are both motivated from an economic perspective as well. Cultural objectives and this is related.” Ramadani stressed that film policies depend on cultural factors and the government's understanding of them. In doing so, she cited the example of Austria, which is in the top five European countries that subsidise the film industry with public funds. She attributed the reasons for this result to the film industry's sustainable support programs: “22 public funding institutions in Austria with six operating at the national level and 16 at the regional level.”

Although the second part of the debate was scheduled for experts to debate with the audience, people from the audience had already started asking questions during the first part. One question was asked by a Polish film producer who was curious about the Netflix data: “It's a question about the methodology you used for your financial data, and I was actually really intrigued by what Professor Kowalski said?”. The producer added that Netflix invests large sums of money to produce films and series in Poland, perhaps even more than in other European countries. One reason may be the large audience market (38 million citizens) in Poland. Tadeusz Kowalski noted that Netflix is reluctant to share its statistics. Still, based on conversations with policymakers and Netflix employees, it can be concluded that the streaming platform's annual budget is larger than the public budget dedicated to the development of the film industry in Poland. A media researcher from

Romania, Ioana Avadani from The Center for Independent Journalism, spoke next, outlining the experience of the film industry in Romania. The researcher also referred to the creative process itself, which has changed, citing the example of a Romanian film shot with a smartphone. She noted that technological changes affect not only the film industry but also the media industry: “The photojournalism went down, and Chicago Tribune sacked all the photo departments because reporters can take pictures with the phone. And secondly, we were so happy to support citizen journalism, and now it blows in our faces.” With this, she started discussing the role of information and communication technologies, which radically affect the labour market.

Anita Zawisza raised the issue of following new generations and their ways of using media tools: “TikTok, social media in general, video platforms, that's all changing. We are living in platform, really driven landscapes, and that's true.” In turn, Jacek Mikucki added that the Reboot project is also studying the preferences of young people - generation Z. The study is at the stage of developing results, but it can be seen that one of the results is the use of smartphones to watch all kinds of audiovisual content, including VOD platforms. So, one can see a shift from using large screens to the mobile and compact screens that smartphones offer. Mikucki also stressed the significant role of special effects in films, which are often expected by young filmgoers.

Then, Michal Glowacki steered the conversation towards the role of European cultural heritage in the field of European film. He also referred to the process of archiving audiovisual productions in the era of digitisation, which may also affect the dissemination of national films in the online sphere. Tadeusz Kowalski mentioned the difficulties of digitising films due to the copyrights of filmmakers as well as co-creators, for example, in the area of film music. He said: “If you want to do anything with the old film, is the silent film,” highlighting the legal problem associated with digital archiving. Fernando Ramos Arenas referred to the key role of cultural institutions that are responsible for the dissemination and digitisation of film heritage. Given the development of streaming platforms, digitising older audiovisual productions is advisable. He added that access to digital cultural heritages for the public is important. In turn, Gentiana Ramadani stressed the important role of public service media in film exposure: “Public service medium should distribute films that reflect the societal challenges and identities and values, and of course, serving the public interest. It's very important.”

The audience spoke in the last part of the debate, discussing with the panellists. One of the questions was asked by Milica Pesic, director of the Media Diversity Institute from the UK, who pointed out that film diversity in Europe is very culturally diverse. In doing so, she gave the example of the UK, which culturally differs significantly from so-called continental Europe. Jacek Mikucki also

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added that budgets for film productions vary considerably due to the economic situation in each country. He cited the results of the survey, which indicate that Polish producers have to save on many elements when making a film, citing the term “Ikea Glass productions,” which was used by a person surveyed during the study. He said: “We want to make better quality movies, but the reality is different.” He added that one solution is international co-productions, which increase the quality and value of films and foster European ties.

Another audience member, Alicja Waszkiewicz-Raviv of Warsaw University, referred to the young audience in her statement: “Maybe about creating a link between this tension of technology that we see as accessible for youngsters and, on the other hand, their approach to movies as something that.” She also emphasised the role of film education among young people. Later in the debate, Bissera Zankova of the Media 21 Foundation from Bulgaria spoke, stressing the need for audiovisual education for young people. She also referred to the key role of public service media in distributing and exposing films. She noted that the display of Hollywood productions often dominates many European public service media. In contrast, public service media should follow their principles and values more closely, promoting indigenous and European productions. One of the last to speak was Tadeusz Kowalski, who summed up the debate with the following sentence: “I think that maybe we should also have in mind that it's not only about the competitiveness. It's also about the protection of diversity, protection of language, protection of history, of culture, of generation.”

The workshop provided a valuable platform for practitioners, academics, researchers, policymakers, and film industry professionals committed to driving change and improvement in the European film sector. Bringing together representatives from public institutions supporting film production, filmmakers, researchers, and audiovisual experts, the event fostered a collaborative and inclusive space for sharing research findings, discussing industry challenges, and exchanging best and worst practices in audiovisual production.

Figure 4. Pictures taken at the panel in the Zachęta - National Gallery of Art, January 22 2025

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4.3. UNESCO Sound Week – Nice 2023

The UNESCO Week of Sound, held in Nice from 20 to 29 January 2023, provided a forum for discussing sound-related creativity, technological advancements, and professional trajectories. The event hosted at the Georges Méliès Campus in Cannes, offered a multidisciplinary programme combining artistic creation with technical and professional perspectives, facilitating a holistic examination of contemporary developments in sound studies.

On 27 January, the symposium focused on the symbiotic relationship between sound, digital technologies, and creative methodologies. Franck Dufour introduced the concept of *chansigne*, elucidating the intersemiotic translation mechanisms involved in rendering sign language into musical performance. This aligns with recent research on multimodal communication, which explores how meaning is constructed across different semiotic systems (Kress, 2010). Laurent Koppitz presented the F.A.M.E.S. Project, which engages with novel methodologies in sound production. The day further featured an exposition on the KINO Project by Noah Morris and Lucas Benevaut, followed by an intervention from Julie M. Vaquié and Jean-François Trubert on the Horizon Europe REBOOT Project, which investigates the evolving paradigms of film music composition in the digital era. This discourse resonates with current scholarly inquiry into digital creativity and the reconfiguration of compositional practices through emergent technologies (Born & Devine, 2015).

Subsequent discussions encompassed virtual and immersive soundscapes, as illustrated by Jonathan Bell's presentation of a VR-based virtual instrument, Camille Giuglaris' introduction of the Pré Device, and Maxence Mercier's immersive concert experience. These innovations reflect broader academic dialogue on sound spatialisation and digital lutherie, particularly regarding the ramifications of digital interfaces on auditory perception and musical engagement (Paine, 2018). The day culminated in an overview on pedagogical frameworks in film scoring and music production, underscoring the pivotal role of formal education in shaping professional pathways within these domains.

On 28 January, the event shifted towards professional opportunities in the field of sound. Discussions centred on the role of sound engineers, music publishers, and composers within the creative industries. Corinne Clerissi and Jean-François Trubert introduced the Campus des Métiers et des Qualifications Excellence ICC PACA, an initiative designed to enhance training opportunities in the cultural and creative industries. This aligns with contemporary research on cultural policy and professionalisation in the creative industries, which emphasises the need for interdisciplinary skill development (Flew, 2019). Pierre-Marie Wodarski examined the Cézame music publishing model, while Michel Buffa delineated Web Audio Modules, illustrating the growing relevance of web-based

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sound technologies. Yves Marino concluded the conference with an analysis of the intersection between sound engineering profession, technical expertise and artistic sensibility within contemporary sound production.

4.3. Participation to SAWA Industry Workshop

The SAWA (Screen Advertising World Association) Convention 2024, held from February 11 to 14 at the Hyatt Regency Palais de la Méditerranée in Nice, convened leading figures in cinema advertising, marketing, and audience engagement. The convention addressed the post-pandemic recovery of the cinema industry, the evolution of advertising methodologies, and the impact of emerging technologies on audience interaction.

Kathryn Jacob OBE, President of SAWA, and Julian Pinn, CEO of SAWA, opened the event by situating cinema advertising within the broader transformations of the global media landscape. A keynote by David Hancock (OMDIA) examined cinema's recovery following the COVID-19 pandemic, drawing on economic and behavioral analytics. This discussion aligns with current research on the resilience of cinema as a cultural institution, particularly in the interplay between digital streaming services and theatrical releases (Tryon, 2020).

A key focus of the convention was advertising strategies in the context of shifting consumer behavior and economic uncertainty. Helen Hewlett (Coca-Cola Europacific Partners) analysed the implications of the cost-of-living crisis on audience engagement, complementing ongoing studies on consumer psychology and media consumption (Kantar, 2023). Lucas Hulsebos (DVJ Insights) and Paul Remitz (Omnicom Media Group Germany) further explored data-driven approaches to advertising effectiveness, reflecting industry trends toward attention-based metrics in marketing (Wedel & Pieters, 2019).

The rise of programmatic advertising in cinema was another central theme, discussed by Stefan Kuhlow (Weischer.Cinema), Robert Brown (Cineplex Entertainment), and Mike Rosen (NCM). Their insights underscored the industry's transition toward automation and personalization in advertising strategies, paralleling broader developments in digital marketing (Lambrecht & Tucker, 2019). Additionally, a session led by Tom Bert (BARCO) at the Cinéum in Cannes showcased advancements in High Dynamic Range (HDR) projection technologies, emphasising innovation in cinematic visual standards.

The convention also highlighted academic perspectives on creativity in industry practices. Jean-François Trubert and Julie Mansion-Vaquié (Université Côte d'Azur) on behalf of the Reboot project presented research on film music and sound design, underscoring the interplay between artistic research and industry applications. Their approach aligns with contemporary discussions on the role of academia in creative industries, advocating for stronger collaborations between researchers and practitioners (Hearn et al., 2018).

Figure 5. Pictures taken at the Movie Theatre Cineum During the SAWA Convention, 13th February.

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